

Expounding Motivational Consequence to Teachers Achievement

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ABSTRACT

This research determined the over-all performance of the Senior High School teachers in relation to their motivational factors. This study used a descriptive research. The respondents were the teachers of the Senior High School Department who rendered minimum of 2 years of service were being surveyed. A modified teacher's evaluation instrument was used. The results were validated using the following statistical tools: Percentage, Weighted Mean and the Analysis of Variance. Results of the study show that there is a significant relationship between the motivational factors and the teaching performance of teachers. Human Resource programs of the organization should be enhanced in order to address the needs of the teachers thus increase more motivation and productivity.

KEYWORDS: Motivational Consequence; Secondary teachers Achievement, Descriptive Research

INTRODUCTION

High motivation means high production. If employees are motivated in their work, organization will become productive. In the field of education, teachers play a vital role in imparting their knowledge and expertise to their students in order for their students to grow as an individual. Primary professional asset in a school are teachers. They are considered as moulder and a best agent in developing students a better and productive citizen in our country. Every teacher tries her best to become competent, capable and educationally equipped or qualified to handle the great responsibility of finding solution to any problem that may come. It has been said by many that teachers build a nation and teaching is thought to be the noblest among all professions. Therefore, to meet this expectation, the country seeks quality among teachers. In this sense, a teacher has to update professionally, personally and be rightfully motivated and committed so he/she could discharge his/her diverse tasks and responsibilities with efficiency and effectiveness.

Teacher's motivation has become an important issue given their responsibility to impart knowledge and skills to learners especially that the main goal of educating a child is to nourish all dimensions of life for a holistic development. Teachers' motivation is that drive that is exerted on teachers to improve their professional tasks with enthusiasm (Wilson, 2013).

Research on teacher motivation has evolved and expanded since the early 1990s, and there has also been a marked rise in literature across various social-cultural contexts within the space of teacher motivation assessment. The discharge of the unique problem of teaching motivation through learning and instruction in 2008 was a major discovery, with the primary objective being related (Watt and Richardson, 2008).

Suson (2019) stated that there should be a proposed training's and seminars for the teachers in order for them to grow in this new era.

Background of the Study

This study was mainly anchored to the Hierarchy Theory proposed by Abraham Maslow (1954). The theory suggests that human needs form a five-level hierarchy consisting of physiological needs, safety, belongingness /love, esteem, and self-actualization. Maslow's needs hierarchy was developed to explain human motivation in general. Maslow developed a theory about the rank and satisfaction of various human needs and how people pursue their needs. Within the organization, final compensation and health care are some of the benefits which help an employee meet their physiological needs. Safety needs can be manifested when employees feel safe in their working environment. When this is satisfied, the employee's can focus on feeling as though they belong to the workplace. This can be in a form of having good relationship with the colleagues and supervisors. Once satisfied, the employee will seek to feel as though they are valued and appreciated by their colleagues and their organization. The final step is where the employee seeks to self-actualize; where they need to grow and develop in order to become everything they are capable of becoming.

Another Theory, which this study was anchored is the theory of operant conditioning proposed by Burrhus Frederic Skinner. Operant Conditioning is the term used to describe the effects of the consequences of a particular behavior on the future occurrence of that behavior.

There are four types of Operant Conditioning: Positive Reinforcement, Negative Reinforcement, Punishment, and Extinction. Both Positive and Negative Reinforcement strengthen behavior while both Punishment and Extinction weaken behavior. Positive reinforcement.

Strengthening a behavior. This is the process of getting rewards as a consequence of the behaviour being shown. You make a sale, you get a commission. You do a good job, you get a bonus & a promotion.

Negative reinforcement. Strengthening a behavior. This is the process of having a stressor taken away as a consequence of a behavior. Long-term sanctions are removed from countries when their human rights records improve.

Extinction. Weakening a behavior. This is the process of getting no goodies when do a behavior. So if person does extra effort, but gets no thanks for it, they stop doing it.

Punishment. Weakening a behavior. This is the process of getting a punishment as a consequence of a behavior.

Edwin A. Locke's Range of Affect Theory (1976) is arguably the most famous job satisfaction model. The main premise of this theory is that satisfaction is determined by a discrepancy between what one wants in a job and what one has in a job. Further, the theory states that how much one value a given facet of work (e.g., the degree of autonomy in a position) moderates how satisfied/dissatisfied one becomes when expectations are/aren't met. When a person values a particular facet of a job, his satisfaction is more greatly impacted both positively (when expectations are met) and negatively (when expectations are not met), compared to one who doesn't value that facet.

Labor Code of the Philippines stands a law governing employment practices and labor relations in the Philippines. It prescribes the rules for hiring and termination of private employees; the conditions of work including maximum work hours and overtime; employee benefits such as holiday pay, thirteenth month pay and retirement pay; and the guidelines in the organization.

The Magna Carta for Private School Teachers was being declared to promote and improve the social and economic status of private school teachers, their living and working conditions, their terms of employment and career prospects in orders that they may compare favourably with existing opportunities in other walks of life, attracts and retain in the teaching profession more people with proper qualifications, it being recognized that our private school system plays a vital role in the education of our people.

Motivation greatly affects the performance of teachers. School exists, primarily to educate a child. It is for this purpose that teachers are employed in schools. Teachers are, thus, the most important professionals for any nation's

future. However, without adequate support and resources, teachers will not be motivated although they may be highly qualified. It is sad to note that teachers, the most valuable human resource, are often neglected (Abdo, 2001). One should bear in mind that a nation's strength depends on the high quality of its education system and the strength of such a system, in turn, relies on qualified and motivated teachers. Inspired and motivated are essential in providing quality education.

In the study conducted by Boamah, Richard (2014) in Zambia, it was found out that there is a significant relationship between motivational factors to the performance of employees in their workplace.

Another study conducted in Pakistan by Abdullah Khan (2017) explained the satisfactory results from the banks employees about the define factors can enhance employee motivation towards their jobs. The study illustrated that motivated employees satisfied with their job more delicately and serve the organization and customer, especially in the banks where the employees is directly linked with the customer. Whereas the results shows that the factors not only enhance the employee motivation as well as the factors also enhances their moral and social behavior that tends to improve their work performance.

It was being supported by the study conducted in Laguna Philippines by Callo (2015) which showed that there is a significant relationship between motivational factors and the teaching performance in the following indicators: achievement; recognition ; work itself indicators socializing with other employees during the workday and having a job with minimal amount of pressure in service areas.

Last study conducted in Southwestern University PHINMA about Motivational factors affecting Teacher's performance was conducted in 1996 which become the benchmark of the researcher to have this study. It showed that teachers perform well if they are motivated in their work.

Objective of the Study

Specifically, this sought to answer the following problems: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age and gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service in the institution, appropriate trainings and seminars attended teacher's performance as evaluated by the students and the motivational level of teachers along the following indicators.

Methodology

This study was about the level of motivations and the teaching performance of the teachers in Senior High School Department at Southwestern University PHINMA. This study utilized descriptive research which appraised the relationship of the motivational factors to the teaching performance of teachers in Southwestern University PHINMA. Descriptive statistics utilize data collection and analysis techniques that yield reports of the summary of the measures of central tendency, variation and correlation. This study was guided by the flow of study as indicated in the schema. The input of the study contains the indicators on the motivational level of teachers as to security, monetary, working conditions, social, job status, achievement/responsibility, recognition. The process

contained the transmittal letter, answered questionnaire and the teaching performance rating of teachers. Finally, an action plan was crafted as the output of this research. This study used an adapted-modified questionnaire from the study of Ewayan, A. The questionnaire was used in order to gather information that will address the given problem.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the age and gender of the respondents of this study. It shows that the age of the respondents ranges from 21 to 60 years old. Computations yield that the highest percentage falls in the range of 31-35. Moreover, most of the respondents are female and most of them also clustered in the range of 31-35. It also shows that female instructor is much older than male. It implies that within the age range of the respondents, they are motivated because they have already the experiences and development both personal and professional which enable them to stand out with other teachers.

Civil Status

Table 2 shows the distribution of the respondents as to their civil status. Most of the respondents are female who are married. Respondents who are males are single. The respondents are fairly distributed who have the same percentage (50%) as single and married. It only implies that for single people, they tend to be motivated especially with the monetary aspects and the working environment. They are much satisfied with the nature of their work and of course the benefits. Married people are also motivated to do their tasks given not only because of the monetary aspects but also other benefits like free tuition for their kids or even to their brothers and sisters. Working loads and schedules are also good which enable them to have more time in resting while doing other tasks like checking.

Highest Educational Attainment

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents as to their highest educational attainment. It shows that none of the teachers are a bachelor's degree holder. It indicates that majority of the respondents are a bachelor's degree holder with master units or fifty percent (50%). In this regard, teachers are motivated to pursue their professional studies as part of their professional development. It implies that teachers never stop studying thus pursuing their professional studies. Most of the teachers just have units in the masters course because it is costly and need to spend more time and attention. Despite of this, they are still motivated to continue just like how motivated they are in performing in their work.

Length of Service

It has been observed that the longer the person has in the job, the more motivated he is. Similarly, the longer the teaching experience a teacher has, the better the teaching performance. This is because he achieves mastery in his field of specialization through constant practice and exposure. Table 4 presents the number of years of teaching experience of the Senior High School teachers. As can be gleaned from the table, the longest range of teaching experience is 9 years or more while the shortest is 1-2 years. As shown above, majority of the teachers or four teachers (4) rendered their service in a span of 3-4 years (40%). It implies that the respondents are tenured because of rendering of more than 3 years in the institution. Because of this, it can be implied that teachers are motivated to work and stay in the institution because they are much satisfied with the program and benefits that the institution has.

Seminars and Training Attended

Table 5 shows the seminars and training attended by the teachers. As shown in the table, most of the teachers attended the annual In-Service Training in order to be trained with their unique system being used which is the Dynamic Learning Program. It implies that teachers engage themselves for their personal and development. There’s a continuous learning. Engaging in seminars and trainings is one of the indicators that teachers are motivated to learn new things because they are given such opportunity.

Teachers’ Performance as evaluated by the Students

Teaching performance will determine whether they will stay or leave in their work place. Students have the right of evaluating their teachers since they are the one who know their teachers very well.

Table 6 below shows the teachers’ performance of teachers as evaluated by the students. As shown in the table, majority of the teachers are in the outstanding level. It only shows that teachers perform well in their job thus students are happy at the same time learning. With every indicator of mentioned, teachers are in the outstanding level, meaning they did every tasks given as reflected in the indicators. It only implies that with all the loads handled by the teachers, they still manage to be the best that they can be by assuring that their students are also at their best. No matter how burden it is, they still motivated to teach and give the best that they have.

Table6.

TEACHERS PERFORMANCE AS EVALUATED BY STUDENTS	Mean	Interpretation
• I know the learning targets/objectives for each lesson	4.44	OUTSTANDING
• I regularly receive comments or feedback on my schoolwork/performance.	4.26	OUTSTANDING
• I am recognized when I do well or show improvement in my schoolwork.	4.29	OUTSTANDING
• I am aware of class rules and procedures and I am made to follow them.	4.47	OUTSTANDING
• I receive clear explanations of key concepts.	4.36	OUTSTANDING
• I am often checked by my teacher to see if I understand what he or she is saying.	4.30	OUTSTANDING
• I am asked to work with other students to better understand new information, solve problems, practice skills.	4.32	OUTSTANDING
• I receive additional instruction on concepts that I do not understand.	4.39	OUTSTANDING
• I can ask questions to my teacher if there are concepts that I do not understand.	4.52	OUTSTANDING
• I am asked questions that challenge me to think more deeply about the topic.	4.29	OUTSTANDING
• I am given enough practice activities to help me master a skill or procedure.	4.37	OUTSTANDING
• I receive help and guidance from my teacher when needed.	4.45	OUTSTANDING
• I am guided by my teacher in reviewing important concepts and seeing their connection to a new lesson.	4.40	OUTSTANDING
• I engage in learning tasks and activities for the WHOLE class period.	4.33	OUTSTANDING
• I feel excited about and interested in what we are learning.	4.34	OUTSTANDING
• I am given time to think before and while answering a question.	4.41	OUTSTANDING
• I learn at a pace that is not too fast or too slow but just right.	4.39	OUTSTANDING
• I am motivated to learn because my teacher is enthusiastic and joyful.	4.42	OUTSTANDING
• I am appreciated for good behavior and/or disciplined properly for inappropriate behavior.	4.39	OUTSTANDING
• I feel accepted and cared by my teacher.	4.45	OUTSTANDING
• I see the effort of my teacher to know more about my classmates and me.	4.51	OUTSTANDING
• I feel calm and comfortable because my teacher is in control of the class and his/her emotions.	4.49	OUTSTANDING
• I am given examples by my teacher that show me that I can succeed through hard work.	4.49	OUTSTANDING
• I am encouraged to do my best and to keep on trying.	4.57	OUTSTANDING
OVERALL MEAN		
INTERPRETATION	4.40	OUTSTANDING

Motivation Level of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Job Security	4.31	Very High
Monetary Aspects	4.58	Very High
Working Conditions	4.29	Very High
Social Aspects	4.76	Very High
Job Status	4.72	Very High
Achievement/Responsibility	4.76	Very High
Personal and Professional Upliftment	4.44	Very High
Total	4.55	Very High

The table shows the motivational level of the senior high School teachers in relation to their personal and professional needs. The data showed that social aspects and achievement/responsibility got the highest weighted mean of 4.76 which verbally described as very high. This implies that teachers were very highly motivated. Moreover, working conditions got the lowest weighted mean of 4.29 which verbally described also as very high. This entails those teachers working environment was more that above satisfaction but still noted that it was the lowest. Overall, the motivational level of the senior high school teachers got a total of 4.55 which verbally described as very high. Therefore, the researchers conclude that teachers were highly motivated in the workplace.

Conclusion

Based on the results shown in the previous chapter, we can conclude that motivational factors have a great impact to teacher's performance as shown that there is a significant relationship between these two factors. The theories Hierarchy Theory, Operant Conditioning and Range of Effect are very true. Employees are motivated if their needs are given which make them satisfied as shown in the hierarchy of needs. Reinforcement is also true about motivation. The more a person is reinforced, the more he will become motivated thus yield to productivity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following therefore are recommended:

School administrators may clearly show their teachers that the latter are important members in the workplace by offering them a steady and secure employment if not an assurance of good pay.

Teachers may be offered the opportunity to be trained and developed at work, and work actively for teachers to see the measures as relevant letting them to have the freedom to make decisions.

School administrators must continue doing actions that will enable teachers to be more motivated in order to increase their productivity thus perform well.

Future researchers must research on other potential aspects or factors which can affect the teaching performance of the teachers.

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